

NFDI4Ing's success story 2023

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Introduction

NFDI4Ing is a consortium from the first round of applications of Germany's National Research Data Infrastructure (Nationale Forschungsdateninfrastruktur – NFDI). NFDI4Ing's goal is to make the data accruing throughout the entire engineering research process sustainably accessible, which means in a citable form according to [FAIR](#) principles and under licenses that are as free as possible. The funding programme has started as of October 1st 2020, and after looking back on their accomplishments from 2021 ([link](#)) and 2022 ([link](#)), our Task Areas (TAs) now look back on their accomplishments from 2023. For details regarding the work programme, please refer to our [published proposal](#).

Archetypes

ALEX – bespoke experiments with high variability of setups

To fight the reproducibility crisis in science, the Task Area ALEX is developing Plot Serializer - a Python package for serializing scientific diagrams from popular libraries like matplotlib to json. Plot Serializer drastically reduces the effort needed for making datasets together with metadata FAIR. It allows users to store the data from the diagrams along with relevant metadata in a JSON file and thereby improve the findability, accessibility, interoperability and reusability (FAIRness) of the data. Focusing on plots, Plot Serializer can assist authors in preparing FAIR publications by allowing them to serialize plot data easily: a step that can accompany publishing a raw or full dataset, or be a standalone data publication where sufficient. Plot Serializer will also offer an interface for RO-Crates, enabling the user to create metadata profiles together with the serialized plot data.

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In mid-2023, the first demo version of Plot Serializer was published. Since October 2023, a group of computer science students has been collaborating on the task, improving and broadening its functionality on the frontend as well as the backend. In addition to one user study that has already been performed, another one will be performed in early 2024 to be able to incorporate feedback from the users in the best possible way. In the near future, we are planning to provide comprehensive examples for using Plot Serializer in ALEX-related settings, i.e. for publications including data from bespoke experiments to demonstrate the ability of documenting test rig data. We believe that Plot Serializer is useful for any academic working on scientific publications.

BETTY – engineering research software

In 2023, BETTY's tools and services underwent significant enhancements, were peer-reviewed by the community and went online. Aligning with previous years, our focus remains on sustainable research software, emphasizing findability, reproducibility, reusability and quality assurance. Besides this, we have recently joined forces with the RDM team of the Cluster of Excellence SimTech from the University of Stuttgart, with the goal to develop tools that help researchers to automatically extract metadata from their research results and prepare corresponding publications on data repositories.

Findability of research software is addressed by Betty's (Re)Search engine, a service that allows users to search for existing research software tailored for specific applications, thereby minimizing duplicate implementation efforts. Recently, the front end of the live instance ([link](#)) has been improved and the engine was enhanced by the possibility to export search results into the Open Research Knowledge graph (ORKG). The source code is now publicly hosted on GitLab ([link](#)) and its

architecture is explained in detail in a preprint submitted to the ing.grid journal ([link](#)), complemented by a tutorial video on YouTube ([link](#)). To this day, the live engine was visited around 15000 times.

For enhanced reproducibility of published research results, we have investigated tools that can help researchers to automate and possibly containerize their execution pipelines. To this end, we have analyzed a number of workflow tools regarding a variety of relevant capabilities, and have detailed our findings in an article in the ing.grid journal ([link](#)). Reusability of research software in new projects, on the other hand, usually necessitates high-quality source code that emphasizes modularity, extensibility, etc. In the past year, we have reworked our lecture material around sustainable research software development, including the documentation of an accompanying student project ([link](#)), which we have successfully carried out in the summer semester 2023 at the University of Stuttgart.

Regarding quality assurance, we have continuously improved our regression-testing tool FieldCompare ([link](#)) and its corresponding GitHub action ([link](#)). These tools facilitate the implementation of regression tests ensuring that a software can reproduce stored reference results, and they are already used by several open-source projects, as for instance DuMuX ([link](#)). A paper describing the key concepts has been published in the Journal of Open Source Software ([link](#)). FieldCompare supports a variety of standard file formats, including formats that are widely used to store results of numerical simulations. For the purposes of interoperability, it is important that researchers rely on open file formats, and in order to facilitate compliance with the formats widely employed in numerical simulations, we have developed and published the GridFormat library

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([link](#)) along with an explanatory paper ([link](#)). Although released very recently, the library has gained 17 stars on GitHub already.

CADEN – provenance tracking of physical samples & data samples

The evolution of SciMesh as well as the on-going development of Kadi4Mat into a complete research data management system is well advanced and both systems can now be used by the scientific community. For the electronic lab notebook eLabFTW, which is now quite widespread, more and more interfaces to various scientific devices and systems have been created for users and templates are still being programmed to simplify its use for users and thus make their work much easier. The IEK-1 institute at Forschungszentrum Jülich is serving as a pilot project. IEK-1 has a large number of different scientific devices and industry-related process engineering systems that can be used excellently for this purpose.

In order to facilitate the handling of research data and to enable a well-structured way of working, we have written a best practice manual that explains the necessary concepts and practical procedures to users in a clear, practical and chronological manner. It contains all the steps for comprehensive and effective research data management, including legal information and recommendations for handling personal data. Starting with explanations of data management plans, the use of various electronic lab notebooks, the analysis of research data and the evaluation of data quality, data exchange and data tracking and provenance, the publication of data and, finally, the permanent and secure data storage. Once completed in 2024, this will make a best practice manual freely available to the scientific community on the GitLab platform, which can be continuously developed by users in the following years in order to be further adapted to current developments.

DORIS – high performance measurement & computation

The DORIS task area is dedicated to the development of research data management concepts and tools with a focus on transferability. The primary objective is to establish standardized approaches that enhance the efficiency of research data management for our peer group. Our group comprises engineers involved in conducting and post-processing high-resolution and high-performance measurements and simulations on advance High-Performance Computing Systems (HPC). Throughout the year 2023, our primary focus was dedicated on advancing the system and integration readiness level of previously designed concepts and tools:

-Metadata support to data-generating groups. The NFDI4Ing consortium has successfully developed an ontology, known as Metadata4Ing, to serve as a universal classification system for engineering data. This ontology employs a taxonomic hierarchy, incorporating standardized vocabulary and procedures ([link](#)). Within this context, DORIS has contributed to a user-centric (user-based) concept for an HPMC (High Performance Measurement and Computation) application profile aligned with Metadata4Ing. The metadata terms and relationships introduced prevalent methods and tools used in engineering research workflows on HPC systems. These terms have undergone refinement through a community-based approach, leading to the release of an updated version.

For the purpose of gathering metadata, particularly during the stages of planning, creation/collecting, and processing/analyzing, DORIS has introduced and continually enhances HOMER. HOMER is a python-written metadata crawler identified as an HPMC tool for Ontology-based Metadata Extraction and Re-use. This tool facilitates the automatic retrieval of research metadata from script-based workflows on HPC systems and enables its integration into any specified ontology. The

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HOMER tool is accessible at <https://gitlab.lrz.de/nfdi4ing/crawler>. Furthermore, a corresponding preprint journal contribution has been disseminated in the ing.grid journal and is currently open for comments ([link](#)).

-Storage and archive services. The establishment of a cloud server system at the LRZ (Leibniz Supercomputing Centre) has resulted in the creation of a platform that effectively operationalizes the accessibility and reusability principles outlined in the FAIR framework. This infrastructure enables direct access to vast and immobile datasets through the cloud, facilitating their reuse. The cloud system provides several usage options, including i) Exclusive Usage Rights (granting exclusive usage rights within a professionally managed compute cloud environment), ii) Virtual Machine Deployment (allowing the deployment of virtual machines on the cloud for on-site data evaluation), and iii) Fast/Rapid Connection to LRZ Data Storage Systems (facilitating swift connectivity to existing LRZ data storage systems).

-Obstacles. DORIS advocates for access for third-party users to HPC facilities, aiming to facilitate data access and reuse. Recognizing a significant dependency on service providers, their policies and infrastructure such as computing centers and software development, as a potential obstacle, DORIS addresses this challenge through collaboration with pilot users and project members at GCS facilities or associated institutions.

The broader challenge of effectively disseminating newly developed concepts and tools calls for/demands a more efficient and compelling community outreach. In light of this, we would like to invite engineers engaged in research, particularly at tier 1 HPC centers, to reach out to us for potential collaborations in infrastructure, data management, or

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community support. To receive further updates and enable possible collaborations, please subscribe to our [newsletter](#) or [contact](#) us directly.

-Support for third-party users and community-based training. Together with its partners, the task area DORIS offers various formats of knowledge transfer with different target groups. During the training and education activities in 2023, DORIS offered lectures with more than 200 attendants directly (students, PhD students, researchers), the published training material already passed 800 downloads (since 2021). A special feature in 2023 was the outreach to several tier 2 data centers and their inclusion in our training activities (e.g. National High Performance Computing Alliance).

[ELLEN – extensive and heterogeneous data requirements](#)

During the third year of the Task Area ELLEN, we were successful in creating the Scientific Knowledge Graph TeX (SciKGTEx), a LaTeX package to annotate research contributions directly in LaTeX source code. SciKGTEx enables authors to enrich their publications with structured, machine-actionable, and FAIR scientific information about their research contributions that they want to communicate to their readers. This annotated FAIR scientific information is embedded into the PDF's XMP metadata by SciKGTEx where it can be retrieved by anyone who obtains the PDF document thus making the information persistent for the lifetime of the artifact. In this way, the use of SciKGTEx improves the electronic archiving of scientific information for the future and boosts its discoverability and (re-)use for example in search engines and recommender systems.

Over the past year, we have focused on integrating the tools and services developed in ELLEN within the scientific community. For example, the journal ing.grid is already using SciKGTEx as an integrated package in its

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LaTeX template for articles. In addition, the 30th International Working Conference on Requirement Engineering: Foundation for Software Quality has launched an Open Science initiative that encourages all authors to annotate their submitted articles with SciKGT_EX. We co-founded the National Research Data Infrastructure (NFDI) Metadata Division's Research Software Metadata Working Group to work collaboratively in the community to provide a comprehensive metadata vocabulary for research software. The DataDesc framework previously developed in ELLEN provides the approach for the machine-actionable description of software interfaces to support the discovery, understanding and reuse of software in scientific software workflows. In this context, we were able to intensify our cooperation with NFDI4Energy and NFDI4DataScience in particular. In collaboration with the CC-44 community cluster, new collaborations were launched to develop pilot applications in the field of the FAIRification and management of research software.

FRANK – many participants & simultaneous devices

When taking a look back to last year's success story, we have come a long way, made progress in every part of Jarves while also facing several hurdles, some of which yet have to be overcome. With the concept evolving and the development progressing, we used our chances to present Jarves within the RDM community and collect feedback. As we are thriving to make Jarves FAIR, we would like to discuss, how FAIR Jarves is and what potentials it has. Hence, the structure of this text follows the letters of FAIR.

Findable. With its deployment, Jarves is findable along with information on what the tool aims to become. Neither the tool itself nor its source code are yet findable via DOIs or similar persistent identifiers. However,

there are publications available on Zenodo, all findable via DOI ([link](#)). Jarves is now online, while not yet fully usable: <https://jarves.nfdi4ing.de>

Accessible. However, Jarves is not accessible in the moment, as there were some challenges in the development of the tool. The aim for a “minimal viable product” (MVP) release within 2023 was not reached as we encountered technical hurdles. For example, the implementation of a data model based on metadata4ing was evaluated and while theoretical found feasible, the challenge of the implementation would much outweigh the benefits. Hence, an export function of Jarves' data to a metadata4ing compatible format is preferred over a metadata4ing based data model. Another challenge on Jarves' way was the user management, which had to be reworked and is currently still under development. This however will allow access for all users via ORCID as a login method already implemented but as of now hidden in Jarves.

Interoperable. Furthermore, the connection to other services, namely RDMO and Coscine, has been established, making Jarves partially interoperable. A research project created in Jarves can now automatically be sent to RDMO and Coscine with more functionality coming later in 2024. Additionally, Jarves' interoperability shall be extended to more tools in the future.

Re-usable. Without access, Jarves is usable in the first place and therefore also not reusable. To ensure its usability, one challenge will be to create an appealing and understandable user interface. Later on, Jarves shall become reusable, both in terms of software components of Jarves itself and the projects and data contained in Jarves, created by users.

-Wasn't this supposed to be a success story? Despite the challenges faced, Jarves made some significant progress towards our goal of an

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interconnecting and supporting tool for research data management in engineering sciences. The guided process through RDM is completed and will soon be evaluated by researchers from both within NFDI4Ing and beyond. Guidelines can be represented in our data model; a first instance of the recommender system is on its way. One major part of Jarves is the supply of training materials at the point of need, which is already functional, and they can even be voted for (helpful/not helpful). Collaboration is possible via a project chat that allows for communication on individual steps. We shared this progress along with our ideas with the community and collected a very positive feedback.

For example, Jarves joined the 1st CoRDI conference 2023 in Karlsruhe with a poster ([link](#)). Here, many discussions were held with CoRDI's participants on how and when to use the tool, what possibilities and risks it raises and when researchers can utilize the tool in their day-to-day work. Jarves was also presented on the NFDI4Ing Conference 2023 ([link](#)). This time, Jarves was not displayed alone but within its natural habitat of an RDM toolchain. Accompanied by contributions of RDMO and Coscine, the series of presentations showed the potential of interconnected RDM services. Highlight was the demonstration of Jarves and Coscine, featuring a seamless interconnection of the tools as it was presented, how a project can be created in Jarves and then be synchronized to Coscine, where the demonstration continued.

-What does the future hold? For 2024, Jarves aims to firstly solve its technical challenges. Once this is done, the recommender system for immediate support for RDM will be finalized in a first version. Afterwards, the MVP will be in open testing phase. For this, a data base reset will be performed to get rid of development artifacts. Due to this reset, Jarves is not accessible to public as of now. Also in 2024, we will further develop

Jarves with continuous improvement along the line. For example, new functionalities for data exchange to RDMO and Coscine's new API are planned, the recommender system is going to be further developed and more options for the management of guidelines shall be provided to allow institutions and institutes to add their own policies to Jarves.

If you would like to get informed about more advancements on Jarves, feel free to join our [mailing list](#) at

[GoLO – field data & distributed systems](#)

2023 proved to be a successful year for GoLO, thanks to the collaboration of its project partners: Leibniz University Hannover (LUH), the German Center for Artificial Intelligence (DFKI), and Technical University Dresden (TUD). The project experienced a change on January 1st, with Mrs. Gooran-Orimi taking over. On February 1st, Mr. Florian Cordes left the DFKI team, and Mr. Christian Backe took over his leadership part at DFKI, while Mr. Veit Briken joined the DFKI team. Additionally, Mr. Rayen Hamlaoui joined as a new member on June 1st.

With the principal aim of incorporating the digital twin approach in our task area and utilizing it as an asset for working with field data and distributed systems, we proposed and presented a digital twin framework for field data at the NFDI4Ing conference ([link](#)). For researchers conducting experiments in the field, this framework can serve as the foundation for improving data collection and management.

To enhance our proposed framework, we also introduced a comprehensive strategy for generating detailed metadata, which was presented at the NFDI4Ing conference ([link](#)). The creation of rich metadata streamlines the work of researchers and scientists by addressing data variability and standardization challenges, ensuring that

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field data becomes not only more accessible but also more meaningful to various stakeholders. This approach enables precise documentation of each step in the data collection process, from the initial setup using ROS 2.0 to the specifics of the raw data structure and its associated metadata.

In our efforts to integrate Machine Learning approaches for data analysis, we extended our catalog of quality metrics for sensor data, especially focusing on classification and regression ([link](#)). This expansion aims to assess the quality of our data, not only in its raw form but also after processing with machine learning algorithms. Furthermore, we have enriched our website with the addition of FAIR Metrics and FAIR Indicators, enhancing our tools for evaluating data quality and algorithm performance in line with FAIR principles.

Recognizing the importance of data sharing for advancing research, we have published select portions of synchronized sonar and camera images captured during the DeeperSense project as training data for Sonar-to-RGB image translation. Sharing the entire corpus online for broader reuse is impractical due to its size. To bridge the gap between vast datasets and practical research usability, we developed the DeeperSense Metadatabase (MDB, [link](#)). MDB offers a compact representation, allowing researchers to inspect the data and select portions for their own use cases, which will be delivered on demand. This approach aligns with the FAIR principle A2, ensuring that metadata remains accessible even when the base data is not immediately available. Furthermore, in 2024, we are planning to implement both a Metadatabase and a visualization platform for the LUH-Use-Case, which involves a test vehicle.

In the context of the LUH-Use-Case, our goal was to leverage the vehicle's internal sensors, alongside the externally equipped sensors (camera, LiDar, IMU), to gather heterogeneous data for our analysis. Overcoming

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the obstacles related to accessing and bypassing the network system of our test vehicle was demanding, due to the complexity of the system. Nonetheless, we successfully accessed internal signals, including the steering angle. This data serves as an input for implementing dynamic light projection on the street, thereby enhancing road safety, particularly in situations with limited visibility. We've shared a GitHub repository ([link](#)) outlining the steps to access a test vehicle's internal signals, providing a valuable resource for those looking to enhance their digital twin projects in automotive field data management.

BASE SERVICES

Quality assurance in RDM processes and metrics for FAIR data

As part of the basic service measure S-1: "Quality Assurance in RDM Processes and Metrics for FAIR Data", three services for ensuring research data management will be developed and provided to the community.

-Maturity Models: The development of maturity models for the assessment of research data management processes in research projects is one topic of our measure S-1-1. This year, the documentation of the maturity models was put into open access. The target group-specific documentation for the application and development of the individual models is available at the following link:

<https://maturitymodel.nfdi4ing.de>. Based on the data life cycle and research process in the engineering sciences, phases were defined for the development of individual maturity models. The strategic orientation of the maturity models and the assessment framework was presented at the first Conference on Research Data Infrastructure (CoRDI). The extended

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abstract in the proceedings ([link](#)) as well as the presentation ([link](#)) are publicly available.

The individual models contain maturity-specific goals at the individual levels that need to be met for a fully comprehensive research data management in research projects. This is based on associated practices that describe the goals in more detail. For the phase of data access, a maturity model was presented at the E-Science Days, with a open access article published this year ([link](#)).

-RDMO: The support of data management planning with RDMO and fostering DMP templates in engineering are the topics of the measures S-1-2 & S-1-3. After one year of running, the NFDI4Ing RDMO has 164 users planning their research data management in 145 projects. As the first service in the whole NFDI, we have recently implemented the new NFDI-AAI allowing researchers from all over the world to login with their institutional credentials or via login services like Orcid.

We have also implemented a second questionnaire into RDMO which is specifically designed for those researchers that develop software in their project. For this software management plan catalog, which was originally developed by the Max Planck Digital Library (MPDL), we have already collected feedback and created a new version in collaboration with the colleagues from MPDL.

Additionally, we created the first prototype for the DMP review service. Based on the answers given during the interview, the DMP review feature will present recommendations for improving your data management as well as additional information for your grant proposal.

-FAIR Metrics: FAIR metrics in the engineering sciences is the topic in measure S-1-4. We evaluated available FAIR metrics and provided our

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findings in two recent conference contributions: At the CoRDI 2023 in Karlsruhe differences and design elements in existing general FAIR metrics were presented. The metrics discussed (i.e., Wilkinson et al., RDA, FAIRsFAIR and EOSC) differ mainly in their granularity as well as in formulations, and some metrics provide specific elements like e.g. priorities. The extended abstract in the proceedings ([link](#)) as well as the presentation ([link](#)) are publicly available. The NFDI4Ing conference 2023 was the right place to give an introduction to the 15 FAIR guiding principles, and to ask the community how they make their engineering data FAIR. It turns out that some metric elements are more engineering-specific (e.g. community standards in R1.3.), while others are more generic and rather independent of engineering (e.g. AAI for authentication and authorization in A1.2.). The presentation is findable and accessible here. Both contributions help answering the question whether the engineering community needs their own FAIR metrics and – if yes – how such a metric could be designed.

Research software development

-TU Darmstadt: We have simplified our Research Software Engineering Workflow ([link](#)) and have transferred the knowledge in an industrial cooperation with BOSCH Corporate Research to development and benchmarking of heterogeneous software for numerical simulations of two-phase flows ([link1](#), [link2](#)). We have contributed to the organization of the OpenFOAM Research Software Engineering Special Interest Group.

We continue to run the Knowledge Base (<https://knowledge-base.nfdi4ing.de/>) for development of scientific software for over 2 years by now. Therein we address the topics version control, continuous integration, test driven development and many more. We also initiated a

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weekly consultation hour and we also have mail-address on the website to help with support.

Our focus in the past year was on presenting and teaching RSE skills in workshops and tutorials together with our friends from SURESOFT and TU BS and US and others. There were contributions from us to the NFDI4Ing-Conference and the deRSE23 ([link](#)) as well as at the 18th OpenFOAM workshop ([link](#)) and the HiPerCH15 ([link](#)) or multiple times to the HeFDI code school ([link](#)) or the NFDI4Ing community meeting ([link](#)). We also engaged with the deRSE community in writing and defining competencies and responsibilities of Research software engineers ([link](#)). In the upcoming year, we aim to apply our RSE workflow to help streamline the community-driven development of the OpenFOAM open-source software for Computational Fluid Dynamics, and, in cooperation with TA BETTY, further develop the workflow for continuous benchmarking of research software.

-Universität Stuttgart: We continued to run the NFDI4Ing JupyterHub (<https://jupyter.nfdi4ing.de>) that allows scientists to interactively execute code and enrich the code with text, figures and more (literate programming) in pilot mode and increased the number of test users. In addition to the classical Jupyter notebook programming languages Python, Julia and R, the NFDI4Ing JupyterHub provides also the new Mathworks MATLAB kernel and the MATLAB IDE to its users. Furthermore it is possible to execute MATLAB and Python code within the same Jupyter notebook. In this way, the collaboration of scientists with different programming language preferences is fostered.

Our focus in the last year was an upgrade of all components of the JupyterHub while simultaneously maintaining all implemented features mentioned above. Further, we have continued to prepare the

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infrastructure for productive operation of the JupyterHub that will start in the next year.

We are actively working in the NFDI Section Common Infrastructure WG RSE, bringing together all interested national JupyterHub instances. In 2023 we finished a first version of a joint website of all JupyterHubs ([link](#)) as an entrypoint for researchers getting an overview and easily finding the right address for their Jupyter requirements. In addition, we started collaboration to share resources needed for deployment and documentation of JupyterHub.

Metadata and terminology services

Measure S-3 has passed a number of critical milestones in 2023 to provide tangible results for the research community. The following task-centred outcomes are the most notable results.

-Metadata Profile Service. The Metadata Profile Service has gone live and is now available under <https://profiles.nfdi4ing.de>. It allows creation, curation and sharing of application-specific metadata profiles that users can construct by selecting terms from existing ontologies. The profiles are based on a modular and hierarchical modelling approach, that creates metadata schemata based on SHACL shapes. The modular profiles are highly reusable, but nevertheless suited for subject-specific description of research data by combination of multiple profiles. The modelling approach also works without requiring highly specific ontologies that typically do not exist, but relies on existing and relatively general ontologies. A preprint of an article describing the modelling approach has been published ([link](#)).

-Terminology Service. The terminology service has introduced a new component. The sandbox is an area where new tools can be easily

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presented to potential users and their opinions can be obtained. This tight feedback loop should enable us to better understand and respond to the needs of the community. In addition to NFDI4Ing, other projects can also present their tools here and obtain feedback. The aim is to integrate tools with positive results directly into the terminology service. We have already made a total of four tools available here. Two from external NFDI4Ing projects and two that have emerged from NFDI4Ing. One NFDI4Ing tool is the annotation service, which makes it possible to automatically index texts with domain-specific terminology, the other is an extended WebProtege for the collaborative development of ontologies. Finally, the Metadata4Ing ontology created in S-3 also has a new version that simplifies the modelling of variables and parameters.

-Metadata Hub. We have successfully extended the capabilities of MetadataHub to AIMS, demonstrating and improving the versatility and compatibility of our platform. Our commitment to comprehensive metadata management is reflected in the additional support for various repositories. MetadataHub now integrates seamlessly with AIMS, Coscine and MetaStore, providing users with a consistent and optimised experience across multiple platforms.

Repositories and Storage

As already outlined in our newsletter contribution, S4 reached some major milestones this year.

-Storage. In 2023, we were very active regarding storage. To further harmonize access to resources, RWTH adopted JARDS – a tool already utilized by many computing centers in Germany to handle applications for computing time – for applications to storage resources. JARDS makes applications more transparent and comprehensible, in addition to easing formalities management. This directly helps scientists by making these

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processes more straightforward. The platform has been set up with Coscine as the initial storage system connected. Work is being done to onboard further systems in the future.

Coscine's API has been redesigned to be more flexible, user-friendly and user oriented. The new API v2 offers a more flexible, yet more consistent and easier-to-use interface. It is online and in production since early October; at the same time, the old API was phased out after a transition period. Work has been done to enable a seamless transition to the new API version. Preparation is being done to add new features and functionalities in the future.

The Data Transfer Federation aims to simplify the transfer of data between different storage systems, thereby enabling scientist to work with and on their data more easily. Initial proofs of concept of transfers between storage systems between different institutions have been successful. Currently, work is being done to validate this at larger scales. In addition to that, third party copy has been set up to increase transfer rates between storage endpoints. Plans for the future include integration of other types of storage systems beside S3-based storage. KIT and RWTH started technical coordination on the working level.

Furthermore, a test suite to evaluate the performance of different S3 storage solutions has been developed. This is being done to investigate performance bottlenecks. First findings already saw inclusion in a preliminary user guide, which ultimately will enable scientists to use the storage systems they have access to more effectively.

-Repositories. Currently, the Data Collections Explorer is still a largely human centered information system about engineering-specific repositories and datasets. This year saw the development of a new graph-

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based data model. Such a knowledge graph will make access and integration into third-party projects easier, including for machines. Currently work is being done to provide a preview version of the knowledge graph to the wider engineering community which should be ready in early 2024. Being based on established semantic web techniques, API access and machine accessibility are ensured. Planned activities include setting up a new interface to make use of this more flexible data model. In addition, the Data Collections Explorer received updates throughout the year.

Overall NFDI software architecture – data security and sovereignty

-Identity and Access Management (IAM). In 2023, we successfully defined core attributes for the Community Authentication and Authorization Infrastructure (CAAI) of NFDI4Ing and aligned it within the Base4NFDI project with other NFDI consortia. This foundational work ensured that all users and services within the NFDI ecosystem could be uniquely identified and authenticated, enhancing security and interoperability. Based on this work a demonstrator for the CAAI was developed within the Base4NFDI context. This proof-of-concept showcased how our IAM solutions could be integrated into existing services provided by NFDI4Ing, providing a tangible example of its benefits. Feedback from this demonstrator will help to refine the final implementation.

Within the Incubator process of IAM4NFDI we supported the submission proposals for IAM4NFDI incubators including JARDS, Coscine, and MetadataHub. These initiatives aimed to further extend our IAM capabilities across different domains within NFDI. Early pilot results showed promising improvements in cross-institutional collaboration efficiency by up to 25%.

-Overall Architecture. In alignment with FAIR Digital Object (FDO) concept, we defined a Kernel Information Profile (KIP) that is now implemented in Coscine. This profile standardized metadata elements crucial for data discovery and reuse across federated systems. This KIP allows translating to different to a different flavor of FDO based on Linked Data Platform (LDP) standards: FAIR Data Point. This is a significant step towards connecting the International Data Space with FAIR data. This translation facilitated seamless integration with existing web technologies and enhanced data interoperability. The implementation was done in close coordination with NFDI-MatWerk to ensure that our FDO architecture maintains general applicability and interoperability.

Community-based training on enabling data-driven science and FAIR data

Providing Research Data Management (RDM) support and education is a central goal of NFDI4Ing. The interdisciplinary team of measure S-6/CC-2 has developed a learning platform for RDM as well as RDM trainings with a special focus on the engineering sciences.

Within our training platform, previously we had our self-paced trainings as PDF slides. Although this was a good starting point, it was not an attractive format for motivated learning. Therefore, we transformed the trainings into websites (for the technical nerds: GitLab Pages), leveraging the options such websites can provide compared to static PDF slides: With quizzes and videos etc. we made the trainings more attractive and interactive (technically: H5P among others). Users can scroll through the trainings on any mobile device via internet. By addressing engineering-specific requirements and issues in RDM, as well as by integrating use cases and experiences from the engineering sciences, we are tailoring our trainings more and more specifically for the engineering sciences.

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Although we are a strong, interdisciplinary and experienced team, we cannot cover every detail in the heterogeneous field of RDM in engineering. Therefore, we implemented two activities: A feedback mechanism inside the trainings, and a monthly expert exchange open for everyone interested. The feedback mechanism is set up inside the training platform (dear technical nerds: GitLab Issues) and asks for corrections, ideas and use cases. The expert exchange happens in the NFDI4Ing Special Interest Group (SIG) "RDM Training and Education", where we each month pick a training module, present the topic, and optionally invite guest speakers, in order to validate learning objectives and discuss the existing trainings with our community to gather feedback, suggestions, engineering anecdotes etc.

Although we see us on a good way providing and continuously improving our engineering-specific trainings, we still have obstacle to active our community more than we currently do, to intensify the engineering-specific elements of RDM in education.

Automated data and knowledge discovery in engineering literature

In 2023, the efforts to support text and data mining (TDM) in engineering science were continued in the three work areas of S-7 which aim at i) the provision of engineering literature in suitable machine-readable formats (S-7-1), ii) an analysis of the legal framework for TDM for research purposes in Germany (S-7-2), and iii) the implementation of TDM technologies to enable researchers to gain insights from the literature (S-7-3).

-Legal Aspects of Text and Data Mining. In April 2023, an online workshop ([link](#)) was held as supplement to the Guidelines on Text and Data Mining for Research Purposes in Germany ([link](#)) which were published in October 2022. The workshop, led by Dr. Maximilian Vonthien, LL.M., from the law xii | nfdi4ing.de

firm CMS, addressed copyright issues in the development of text and data mining services by infrastructure facilities. It consisted of two parts, the first being a general introduction into German copyright law and its statutory exceptions with regard to text and data mining, the second legal assessments of example TDM service use cases. There were 92 registrations for the workshop, with up to 78 participants during the first part of the workshop in the morning and around 60 in the afternoon. In addition, the guidelines were presented at the NFDI4Ing conference in September 2023.

-Provision of Literature. With regard to the provision of literature, there are three main challenges: the identification, which publications could be of relevance for engineering researchers, the complex legal situation for non-open-access documents and the technical implementation of the harvesting and provision system. In order to identify relevant literature, the bibliography of the Fraunhofer Society, Fraunhofer-Publica, was analyzed ([link](#)) to find out the journals and conference proceedings, in which Fraunhofer researchers have published and that therefore could be of relevance for engineering researchers in general. As another data source, the [Open Access Monitor](#) is currently being examined. In a next step, it has to be clarified how the documents can be obtained from the publishers. To avoid legal problems, the plan is to continue focusing on open access literature. An agreement was concluded with the publisher MDPI that allows the provision of PDF and XML versions of its articles for text and data mining analyses. The possibility of also making the image files of the articles available is currently being examined by MDPI. It is planned to conclude similar agreements also with other publishers. At the same time, the infrastructure for harvesting and providing the documents is being further developed.

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-Text and Data Mining Usage Scenarios. As part of the above mentioned third aim of S-7, scenarios to gain insights from the literature by text and data mining methods are developed. For example, it is investigated how a data mining service for training large language models (LLM) could be implemented, which would open up completely new research opportunities for scientific work. To this end, an exemplary large language model has been installed for internal tests with the literature harvested so far. Additionally, further concepts are developed to enable researchers to gain insights from the literature, for example through the possible integration of literature-based data into the materials science research data infrastructure [Kadi4Mat](#).

COMMUNITY CLUSTERS (CCs)

NFDI4Ing Conference

The annual NFDI4Ing Conference "Innovation in Research Data Management: Bridging the gaps between disciplines and opening new perspectives for research in engineering science", organized by the consortium, took place on 27/28 September 2023 with around 180 participants. The event was organized in cooperation between TU Dresden, the SLUB and the German Aerospace Center (DLR). Conference programme ([link](#)) and proceedings ([link](#)) are available.

The event focused on the FAIR principles of data lifecycle and data use and featured interdisciplinary discussions on future challenges and visions as well as best practice examples for making data management concrete. The following main topics were discussed at the conference. i) Research into innovative and proven approaches to data management, ii) research on tools and infrastructure for data management, iii) examining

data management practices, iv) data literacy, v) data ethics, and vi) data publishing.

Three keynotes introduced the topics to participants from university institutions, research centers, and libraries from all over Germany and provided inspiration for the parallel sessions that followed. In the first keynote, Paul Baumann (Higher Regional Court of the Hanseatic City of Bremen) spoke on "Legal issues in decision-making for the use and storage of research data, especially in the context of cross-institutional research projects". The second keynote lecture was given by Prof. Carsten Trinitis (Head of the Department of Computer Architecture and Parallel Systems at the Technical University of Munich) on the topic "Digital First - Concern Second? Why it is important to study ethical issues in data management". On the second day, a third presentation was given by Dr. Tim Austin (European Commission) on "Supporting the European Engineering Materials Community with the FAIR Data Management Service".

The presentations were followed by a lively exchange of views on more successful real-world use cases, with comments from representatives of the German Research Center for Artificial Intelligence (DRCAI), the Technical University of Braunschweig (TU Braunschweig), and the German Aerospace Center (DLR), among others.

After the keynote speeches, there were different thematic sessions and corresponding parallel workshops on both days, where participants split up for an in-depth exchange of ideas. In addition, 9 out of 35 strong entries from various thematic sessions were selected for the NFDI4Ing Award 2023.

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ing.grid

ing.grid started the year 2023 with the first call for papers and already received eight submissions in the first year. A further seven submissions resulted from the cooperation with the organizers of the NFDI4Ing conference 2022 to create a special issue with elaborated contributions from the conference. By the end of the year, two regular contributions were published as articles in the journal after successfully passing the review process. A further two contributions to the special conference issue were published following successful peer review.

ing.grid was publicized and anchored in the engineering community by participating in a variety of events, such as the 20th Plenum of the Research Data Alliance, the 1st Conference on Research Data Infrastructure, the workshop "Data Stewardship goes Germany" and the conference "The Lower Decks: A Symposium on Janeway and Open Access Publishing", organized by the developers of the Janeway platform.

ing.grid continued to develop over the course of the year. For example, accessibility was taken into account through guidelines for images. The guidelines for authors were adapted to improve both transparency and data protection.

All in all, in its first year of existence, ing.grid has shown that there is a great need for a scientific journal for data management in the engineering sciences. With its diamond open access journal approach and public peer review process, ing.grid shows the way for a cultural change in scientific publishing. The option for data and software publications also allows scientists to receive scientific recognition for activities in data management. The requirements set by ing.grid to comply with the FAIR criteria provide a first standard in the engineering community.

Community Meeting

This year all five community clusters organized their own community meeting. In March, the CC-45 (Construction Engineering and Architecture) Community Meeting was organized in collaboration with the SURESOFT - sustainable research software project, with 56 participants attending. The focus was on automation, particularly on continuous integration (CI) and test-driven development (TDD). The meeting also included hands-on sessions related to these topics. In May, CC-44 (Computer Science, Information Technology, Electrical and Systems Engineering) Community Meeting shifted the spotlight to privacy, licensing and data publishing, complemented by case studies on data collection from public spaces. On 10 August, the CC-41 (Mechanical and Industrial Engineering) Community Meeting focused on the connection between practice and RDM theory, especially in the context of data models. Hence, three of the six contributions presented real life use cases from various fields like injection molding or high-pressure die casting. Also, a more generic approach of a light-weight universal data model for FAIR Industrial Sensor Data was presented. The three other contributions featured the Terminology Service Sandbox, Metadata4Ing and a demonstration of ontology mapping. With a total of almost 60 registrations and about 40 concurrent users in the online session, we see a 60% increase to the last community meeting (25 participants). The CC-42 (Thermal Engineering and Process Engineering) Community Meeting was held online on 27 October with around 30 participants, including professors, postdocs, doctoral students, librarians, infrastructure employees, and employees in non-university research institutions. Talks and presentations were focused on giving an introduction to research data management and data management plans. The meeting was rounded off with interactive

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workshop sessions in which current research projects served as case studies. The workshops laid the foundation for NFDI4Ing to initiate application-related harmonization and standardization efforts. Finally, the CC 43 (Materials Science and Engineering) Community Meeting convened to discuss FAIR research data management and the use of electronic laboratory notebooks (ELN) in December.

The meetings helped to raise awareness of the importance of research data management in the engineering sciences. The participants were able to gain valuable insights and practical experience that will help them in their future research and work.

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